

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DURATION OF TYPE II DIABETES AND HEPATIC STEATOSIS: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON LIVER FAT ACCUMULATION

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE: To compare the association between duration of type II diabetes mellitus and hepatic steatosis.

METHODOLOGY: This research utilized a cross-sectional study design and was carried out in the Department of General Medicine at Dr. Ruth K.M. Pfau Civil Hospital, Karachi. A total of 186 participants were recruited using a non-probability consecutive sampling method. The study population comprised individuals aged between 30 and 80 years, regardless of gender, who had been diagnosed with type II diabetes mellitus (T2DM) for at least one year.

To assess hepatic steatosis, all participants underwent an abdominal fibroscan ultrasound. Data was collected systematically and analyzed using SPSS software version 26.0.

RESULTS: The mean \pm standard deviation of age was found to be 54.32 ± 8.07 years. Among them 45.7% were and 54.3% were female patients. The mean \pm standard deviation of body mass index (BMI) was noted as 25.85 ± 3.67 kg/m². Obesity was documented in 49.5% of participants, hypertension 64.0%, dyslipidemia 23.7% and hypertriglyceridemia was noted in 31.2%. The prevalence of steatosis was identified in 61.2% of patients with type II diabetes mellitus. Those with steatosis had a significantly shorter duration of diabetes as compared to those without steatosis (11.23 ± 3.82 v/s 12.44 ± 4.28 years, $p=0.045$).

CONCLUSION: The results of this study reveal a notable prevalence of hepatic steatosis among individuals with T2DM, showing a significant correlation with the duration of the disease. These insights emphasize the necessity for routine screening in diabetic patients to enable early identification and timely management. The implementation of such proactive measures can improve preventive and therapeutic modalities thus improving patient care and reducing the complications of diabetes mellitus.

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is among the fastest-growing chronic conditions globally, contributing

significantly to the rising prevalence of diabetes-related complications. In 2021, approximately 537

million individuals were diagnosed with diabetes worldwide, and this number is projected to increase to 783 million by 2045 [1]. As a persistent metabolic disorder, diabetes imposes a substantial burden on healthcare systems, economies, and the well-being of affected individuals and their families. The financial impact is significant, with direct healthcare expenditures for diabetes reaching approximately USD 966 billion in 2021 [2].

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) has emerged as the most prevalent chronic liver condition, posing a growing global health challenge [3,4]. With the increasing prevalence of T2DM, a corresponding rise in NAFLD cases has been observed, suggesting a strong interconnection between the two conditions [5]. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is regarded as one of the possible risk factors that may promote the progression of NAFLD to more aggressive stages of disease like non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), advanced fibrosis and cirrhosis [6]. Both T2DM and NAFLD are frequently accompanied by pathophysiological pathways that may contribute to this association, including insulin resistance, metabolic dysfunction, and increased hepatic lipotoxic exposure [7].

High fatty liver is consistently associated with an increased risk of diabetes [8–10]. Abstract NAFLD is mainly featured by the excessive fat storage in hepatocytes which cause hepatic steatosis. Diagnosis is made by the presence of hepatic steatosis, lobular inflammation and hepatocellular ballooning, with or without fibrosis [11]. Availability of hepatic steatosis provoking liver dysfunction and inflammation, as well as insulin resistance (IR), can worsen metabolic abnormalities [12,13]. Insulin resistance is a major player in the pathogenesis of T2DM, and thus, if persistent, may affect the severity and natural history of NAFLD [14].

In addition, ongoing hyperglycemia and mild chronic inflammation associated with well-established T2DM can induce enhancement of hepatic fat deposition and fibrogenesis [12,13]. The duration of diabetes is also a key rationale because prolonged metabolic dysregulation drives extra hepatic complications including NAFLD [6]. This relationship between diabetes and NAFLD is important because diabetic patients with NAFLD have a higher morbidity and mortality rate due to their complications [14].

This study aims to examine the association between the duration of T2DM and the severity of hepatic steatosis. While prior research has extensively explored the prevalence of NAFLD in diabetic patients, limited data exist on how diabetes duration influences disease progression. Identifying this link will help improve risk stratification and screening strategies for early intervention, ultimately mitigating long-term complications in affected individuals.

METHODOLOGY

It was a cross-sectional study conducted at the Department of General Medicine, Dr. Ruth K.M. Pfau Civil Hospital, Karachi. The sample of 186 participants were sampled using non-probability consecutive sampling. The population studied consisted of male and female patients aged 30 to 80 years with a confirmed diagnosis of type II diabetes mellitus (T2DM) for at least one year, based on a history of ongoing use of insulin or oral antidiabetic medication for at least 1 year. Participants with pre-existing conditions such as renal failure, chronic liver disease, malignancy, cardiovascular disorders, thyroid dysfunction, a history of cholecystectomy, substance abuse, or prolonged steroid use were excluded. Additionally, individuals who declined to provide informed consent were not considered for participation. Informed consent was obtained after a detailed explanation of the study's objectives, potential risks, and benefits. Recruitment was conducted through the outpatient department of internal medicine. Relevant demographic and clinical information was recorded using a structured data collection tool. Hepatic steatosis was evaluated using an abdominal fibroscan ultrasound, with diagnostic indicators including increased liver echogenicity (bright liver appearance), obscuration of vascular markings, and narrowing of the hepatic vein lumen. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 26.0. Descriptive statistics were utilized to summarize findings, with continuous variables expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and categorical variables presented as frequencies and percentages. A Chi-square test was applied to evaluate the relationship between T2DM duration and hepatic steatosis, with a p-value of <0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Demographic and clinical and biochemical characteristics of the 186 study participants are shown in Table I. The mean age was 54.32 ± 8.07 years, of which 30–55-year old age group contributed 53.8% while age greater than 55 years contribute 46.2%. Of the participants, 45.7% were men and 54.3% were women. The mean BMI was 25.85 ± 3.67 kg/m². Waist circumference (WC) was 101.34 ± 9.76 cm with 50.0% for 85–100 cm and 50.0% for >100 cm. The mean time since diabetes onset was 11.70 ± 4.04 years with most (67.7%) having diabetes for between 4–12 years. The average systolic blood pressure (SBP), and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) recorded were 136.72 ± 9.30 mmHg, and 81.21 ± 10.28 mmHg, respectively.

Regarding liver enzyme levels, ALT (30.45 ± 6.65 U/L) was elevated in 57.5% of the participants, while AST (33.97 ± 13.71 U/L) was elevated in 46.8%. Elevated LDL levels (>95 mg/dL) were observed in 58.1% of patients, while 48.4% had low HDL levels. Among the study population, 49.5% were classified as obese, 64.0% were hypertensive, 23.7% had dyslipidemia, 31.2% had hypertriglyceridemia, and 32.3% were identified as smokers.

Table II: Clinical and biochemical characteristics of participants with hepatic steatosis and those without hepatic steatosis. The mean age of the cohort was not statistically significant higher among those with steatosis (54.61 ± 9.19 years) compared to those without (53.85 ± 5.89 years; $p=0.529$). Compared to patients without steatosis, patients with hepatic steatosis showed a trend towards higher BMI (26.13 ± 3.73 kg/m² and lower waist circumference (100.62 ± 9.77 cm), found to be insignificant ($p=0.189$ and $p=0.209$, respectively). Importantly, the duration of diabetes was significantly lower in those with steatosis (11.23 ± 3.82) years than those without steatosis (12.44 ± 4.28 years, $p=0.045$). There were no statistically significant differences among liver enzymes (ALT, AST) or other biochemical markers ($p>0.05$).

In the hepatic steatosis group, 43.9% (% [SE]) were male and 56.1% were female. Conversely, the composition by gender in the non-steatosis group was similar, with 48.6% males and 51.4% females. The variation in male and female distribution was not statistically-meaningful ($p=0.526$), and thus gender

did not appear to contribute to the presence of hepatic steatosis in this cohort.

The percentage of participants with hepatic steatosis who had hypertension was higher than that of the participants in non-steatosis (68.4% vs 56.9%). This trend implied that the frequency of hypertension was higher in patients with hepatic steatosis but did not reach a statistical significance ($p=0.112$).

Dyslipidemia was notably more frequent in individuals with hepatic steatosis, with 29.8% of participants in this group affected, compared to 13.9% in those without steatosis ($p=0.013$). The statistically significant association suggests a strong correlation between lipid abnormalities and hepatic steatosis. Dyslipidemia contributes to lipid accumulation in hepatocytes, a hallmark of hepatic steatosis, highlighting its role as a potential metabolic risk factor in this population.

Hypertriglyceridemia was observed in 36.0% of patients with hepatic steatosis compared to 23.6% in those without the condition. Although this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.076$), the trend aligns with existing evidence linking elevated triglyceride levels to hepatic fat accumulation. This association underscores the metabolic dysfunction observed in individuals with hepatic steatosis and T2DM, reinforcing the need for early intervention strategies.

DISCUSSION

The onset & progression of hepatic steatosis, also known as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), are significantly influenced by the length of time that a person has type II diabetic mellitus (T2DM) [15]. The main features of type 2 diabetes, long-term insulin resistance and permanent hyperglycemia, aggravate metabolic dysfunction and finally lead to hepatic fat infiltration [16]. Type 2 diabetes promotes a spillover of free fatty acids (FFAs) into liver due to the chronically impaired ability of insulin to inhibit lipolysis [17]. As a consequence, hepatocytes store surplus amounts of triglyceride along with an increased de novo lipogenesis, stimulated by hyperinsulinemia. This metabolic disequilibrium becomes ever more amplified with chronic oxidative stress and chronic inflammation, precipitating the evolution of hepatic steatosis into more advanced

lesions such as cirrhosis, fibrosis and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) [18].

A number of studies have documented the association of the duration of T2DM with the severity of hepatic steatosis [3–5]. Patients with T2DM for more than 10 years are especially susceptible to advanced liver disease due to the persistent risk of hyperglycemia and metabolic derangements [19]. Coexisting conditions such as obesity, dyslipidemia and sedentary lifestyles interact to further hasten the development of liver damage. Furthermore, in chronic diabetic individuals, alterations in the gut-liver axis with increased gut permeability and endotoxemia induce hepatic inflammation.

To reduce the chance of developing severe liver disease, people with type 2 diabetes must have their hepatic steatosis diagnosed and treated in the initial phase. In this high-risk group, diagnostic procedures like elastography, ultrasonography and liver function tests should be used often.

Lifestyle changes including weight loss through food adjustments and increased physical activity, are effective management techniques. Hepatic fat content has been demonstrated to decrease with calorie restriction and a Mediterranean diet high in polyunsaturated fatty acids [20]. Regardless of weight reduction, exercise—both aerobic and resistance training—improves insulin sensitivity and lowers liver fat. Pharmacological treatments are also of utmost importance. GLP-1 receptor agonists, sodium-glucose co-transporter-2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors and metformin are among the medications that have shown promise in lowering hepatic fat and enhancing glycaemic management [21]. Novel treatments that target inflammation, fibrosis, and hepatic lipid metabolism, like agonists of the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR), have promise for treating advanced illness.

In our study, hepatic steatosis was noted in 114 (61.29%) diabetic patients with a mean duration of diabetes in patients with hepatic steatosis as compared to those without hepatic steatosis as 11.23 ± 3.82 and 12.44 ± 4.28 years. A study by Kanwal S, et al reported hepatic steatosis in 61.5% of cases [22]. The study also reported that the mean duration of diabetes was higher in patients with hepatic steatosis as compared to those without hepatic steatosis (13.58 ± 6.41 vs 11.74 ± 6.08) [22]. The study by Chen J, et al stated

the frequency of hepatic steatosis to be 67.6% [23]. In another study, hepatic steatosis was prevalent in 56.4% of patients [24]. A study found the prevalence in 78.72% of patients with a mean duration of diabetes in patients with and without hepatic steatosis as 11.46 ± 8.53 and 12.12 ± 9.09 years [25].

These findings of high incidence of hepatic steatosis similar to previous reports further support the routine consideration of hepatic steatosis in the management of type II diabetes. The trends of diabetes duration were very similar, but the small difference observed highlights the need to study other risk factors and geographical variations of risk factors that may affect hepatic steatosis. The relevant factors contributing to these differences could be examined in future studies, preferably to obtain a comprehensive view on the dynamics of the disease in a varied population.

Patients with type 2 diabetes should undergo routine screening for hepatic steatosis particularly if they have had the condition for a long time or have other risk factors such as obesity, and dyslipidemia. Since it prevents the buildup of hepatic fat and slows the course of the disease, optimal glycemic control should continue to be a fundamental component of diabetic care. The significance of dietary changes, and consistent exercise in enhancing metabolic health, and lowering liver fat should be communicated to the patients. Treatment plans should include drugs that target both T2DM and hepatic steatosis, such as SGLT-2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists. Patients at risk, can receive complete care if diabetologists, hepatologists, dietitians & physiotherapists work collectively. To investigate new treatments and create recommendations for groups like South Asians, who have a high incidence of type 2 diabetes, and hepatic steatosis, further research is needed. The length of T2DM has a prominent impact on the onset and course of hepatic steatosis, and in order to avoid liver-related complications in this high-risk group, a proactive strategy that includes early diagnosis, lifestyle changes, ideal glycaemic control, and targeted therapies is crucial.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study reveal a notable prevalence of hepatic steatosis among individuals with T2DM, showing a significant correlation with the duration of the disease. These insights emphasize the necessity for

routine screening in diabetic patients to enable early identification and timely management. Implementing such proactive measures can enhance both preventive

and treatment strategies, ultimately contributing to better patient outcomes and a reduction in complications associated with diabetes.

Table I: Characteristics of Study Participants (n=186)	
Variable	n (%)
Age (Mean ± SD) = 54.32 ± 8.07	
30-55 years	100 (53.8)
>55 years	86 (46.2)
BMI (Mean ± SD) = 25.85 ± 3.67	
20 - 26 kg/m ²	118 (63.4)
>26 kg/m ²	68 (36.6)
Waist Circumference (Mean ± SD) = 101.34 ± 9.76	
85 - 100 cm	93 (50.0)
>100 cm	93 (50.0)
Duration of Type 2 DM (Mean ± SD) = 11.70 ± 4.04	
4-12 years	126 (67.7)
>12 years	60 (32.3)
Systolic Blood Pressure (Mean ± SD) = 136.72 ± 9.30	
120-135 mmHg	105 (56.5)
>135 mmHg	81 (43.5)
Diastolic Blood Pressure (Mean ± SD) = 81.21 ± 10.28	
65-80 mmHg	102 (54.8)
>80 mmHg	84 (45.2)
ALT (Mean ± SD) = 30.45 ± 6.65	
10-30 U/L	79 (42.5)
>30 U/L	107 (57.5)
AST (Mean ± SD) = 33.97 ± 13.71	
8-35 U/L	99 (53.2)
>35 U/L	87 (46.8)
LDL (Mean ± SD) = 91.29 ± 17.13	
60-95 mg/dl	78 (41.9)
>95 mg/dl	108 (58.1)
HDL (Mean ± SD) = 33.12 ± 7.25	

20-35 mg/dl	90 (48.4)
>35 mg/dl	96 (51.6)
Gender	
Male	85 (45.7)
Female	101 (54.3)
Obesity Status	
Obese	92 (49.5)
Non-Obese	94 (50.5)
Smoking status	
Smoker	60 (32.3)
Non-Smoker	126 (67.7)
Hypertension	
Hypertensive	119 (64.0)
Non-Hypertensive	67 (36.0)
Dyslipidemia	
Yes	44 (23.7)
No	142 (76.3)
Low HDL	
Yes	70 (37.6)
No	116 (62.4)
Hypertriglyceridemia	
Yes	58 (31.2)
No	128 (68.2)

BMI: Body Mass Index, *DM*: Diabetes Mellitus, *ALT*: Alanine aminotransferase, *AST*: Aspartate aminotransferase, *LDL*: Low-Density Lipoprotein, *HDL*: High-Density Lipoprotein

Variables		Hepatic Steatosis		95% C. I	P-Value
		Yes (n=114)	No (n=72)		
Age in years, Mean ± SD		54.61 ± 9.19	53.85 ± 5.89	-1.634~3.168	0.529
BMI in kg/m ² , Mean ± SD		26.13 ± 3.73	25.40 ± 3.54	-0.361~1.814	0.189
WC in cm, Mean ± SD		100.62 ± 9.77	102.47 ± 9.70	-4.744~1.045	0.209
Duration of DM in years, Mean ±SD		11.23 ± 3.82	12.44 ± 4.28	-2.406~ -0.026	0.045
Systolic BP in mmHg, Mean ± SD		136.30 ± 9.87	137.39 ± 8.35	-3.858~1.677	0.438
Diastolic BP in mmHg, Mean ± SD		80.53 ± 10.56	82.29 ± 9.78	-4.816~1.285	0.255
ALT in U/L, Mean ± SD		30.33 ± 6.72	30.63 ± 6.56	-2.271~1.688	0.772
AST in U/L, Mean ± SD		34.07 ± 13.34	33.81 ± 14.37	-3.818~4.348	0.898
LDL in mg/dl, Mean ± SD		90.31 ± 17.64	92.85 ± 16.30	-7.630~2.550	0.326
HDL in mg/dl, Mean ± SD		33.10 ± 7.60	33.15 ± 6.71	-2.216~2.104	0.959
Gender	Male, n (%)	50 (43.9)	35 (48.6)	0.457~1.493	0.526
	Female, n (%)	64 (56.1)	37 (51.4)		
Obesity, n (%)		62 (54.4)	30 (41.7)	0.920~3.030	0.091
Smoking Status, n (%)		37 (32.5)	23 (31.9)	0.544~1.926	0.942
Hypertension, n (%)		78 (68.4)	41 (56.9)	0.889~3.019	0.112
Dyslipidemia, n (%)		34 (29.8)	10 (13.9)	1.209~5.743	0.013
Low HDL, n (%)		47 (41.2)	23 (31.9)	0.804~2.778	0.203
Hypertriglyceridemia, n (%)		41 (36.0)	17 (23.6)	0.935~3.533	0.076

BMI: Body Mass Index, **WC:** Waist Circumference, **DM:** Diabetes Mellitus, **BP:** Blood Pressure, **ALT:** Alanine aminotransferase, **AST:** Aspartate aminotransferase, **LDL:** Low-Density Lipoprotein, **HDL:** High-Density Lipoprotein

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